

Three dimensional woven bone tissue engineering scaffolds of melt-spun poly(lactic acid) fibers

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INTRODUCTION

The loss of bone mass increases and the bone quality deteriorates over the lifespan. As people live longer and expect to feel better, bone damage and fractures are even more serious health problems today than in the past and the need for human “spare parts” thus increases. The need for implants today is far greater than can be met by human donors. Since ethical concerns are raised, the ability to take advantage of organs from animals has been limited [1]. Therefore, demand and knowledge of new technologies for tissue replacement are very high. In recent years, advances in cell biology and production of polymeric materials have opened up opportunities for a new surgery. Polymers are at the focus of the new technology known as tissue engineering [1-3].

The objective of tissue engineering is to allow tissue specific cells to grow, in the body and/or *in vitro* before implantation, over a scaffold, which temporarily occupies mechanical load and then gradually is reabsorbed as the bodies’ own tissue regenerates [4, 5]. A scaffold is usually based on biodegradable materials [6] and tissue engineering has become a promising alternative to current surgical therapies since it may overcome the shortcomings of the methods used today [3].

Some of the challenges in tissue engineering lie in the design and fabricating scaffolds according to its intended applications. When designing and fabricating a scaffold there are a number of basic requirements to fulfill such as high porosity, pore size and shape, surface area and topography, mechanical strength, biodegradability and biocompatibility [2, 7-9]

The design criteria for hard tissue, such as bone which is the target of this study, are a very stiff polymeric scaffold [7]. Woven textile technologies with recent advances in the field of synthetic bioresorbable fibers have this potential because: (a) fibers are a desirable scaffold matrix material due to providing a large surface area to volume ratio, (b) they can be easily processed into a variety of shapes and sizes in order to obtain the desired mechanical and biological properties and (c) weaving techniques are a good choice since a woven fabric is typically stronger, stiffer and less flexible compared to knits and nonwovens.

In this study poly(lactic acid) (PLA) fibers were produced to serve as a scaffolding material for medical applications using melt spinning process, that has advantages compared with solution spinning (i.e. dry and wet spinning) and electrospinning because of its ability to produce fibers from a solvent-free process that provides a more economical and ecofriendly route. Another advantage is that the production speeds are normally higher. The melt-spun PLA fibers were characterized in terms of the tensile- and thermal properties using tensile testing, differential scanning calorimetry, dynamic mechanical thermal analysis and their biodegradability using simulated body fluid (SBF). The relevance of draw ratio and drawing temperatures was clearly supported by the results of these analysis methods. It was shown that the physical properties, such as degree of crystallinity, mechanical strengths, and cross-section of the fibers can be controlled to a great extent by using a continuous two-step melt spinning process, i.e. melt extrusion and hot drawing. Finally, a three-dimensional structure was successfully woven and

investigated. The overall conclusion was that the woven scaffolds from melt-spun PLA fibers have a promising outlook for the future in developing medical scaffolds for bone tissue engineering.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Poly lactide (PLA; NatureWorks® 6201D, melt spinning-grade) was obtained from NatureWorks® LLC, MN, USA. Prior to processing the PLA pellets were dried to avoid degradation due to hydrolysis during manufacturing in a convection oven at 80°C for 4 hours. Phosphate buffered saline (PBF, bioreagent grade) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Co. Ltd. All polymers and chemicals were used as received.

Melt-spinning and drawing of PLA fibers

PLA fibers were produced using a piston spinning machine from FOURNÉ Polymertechnik GmbH, Germany, in a two-step melt spinning process, i.e melt extrusion and hot drawing. The PLA pellets were melt spun into fibers through a circular monofilament spinneret (D=1.0 mm) under argon flow. The melt extrusion temperature and the maximum pressure of the piston were set at 180°C and 1.33 cm³/min, respectively. The as-spun fibers were collected at a wheel speed rate of 8.9 m/min. Hot drawing was then carried out by passing the fibers around a heated godet, then through a second heated godet and finally onto a take-up winder. Draw ratios (DR) of 3-6 were employed at drawing temperatures, 65, 70 and 75°C.

Tensile testing

Mechanical properties of the fibers were evaluated using a tensile testing machine (Tinius Olsen H10KT, Salfords, UK) with single bollard grips (reference HT 33) and controlled by software QMat. The tensile measurements were performed with a load cell of 250 N at a crosshead speed of 12 mm/min and an initial grip separation of 50 mm. Testing was performed at room temperature. Before testing, the mean linear density was calculated from the weight of five meters from the fibers. The average value of at least 6 replicates per each sample was presented with standard deviation.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

The thermal behaviour of the fibers was measured with a Q800 DSC (TA® Instruments) at a heating rate of 20°C/min under nitrogen atmosphere. The heat of fusion of an infinitely large crystal was taken as 93.7 J/g [10] and the degree of crystallization was calculated according to the following equation.

$$X_c^{\text{DSC}}(\%) = 100(\Delta H_m - \Delta H_c) / 93.7$$

where X_c , ΔH_m and ΔH_c are, respectively, the degree of crystallinity (%), the melting enthalpy, and the enthalpy of crystallization.

Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis

DMTA was carried out using Q800 DMTA (TA® Instruments). A fiber was placed in film/fiber tension clamp with an initial clamp separation of 10 mm, pretension of 10mN and oscillated at the frequency of 1 Hz. The heating rate was 3°C/min and the amplitude of 15µm was used in order to remain within the linear visco-elastic range.

Optical microscope

The morphology of the melt-spun fibers was investigated by using a Nikon optical microscope and NIS-Elements image analysis software after calibration. The microscope was operated at 63 times to visualize the samples.

Scanning electron microscope

To clarify if voids and micro cracks were presented in the fibers, the cross section prepared by a scalpel and the surface were analyzed in a Hitachi S-4800 FE-SEM. The test specimens were stored in a Denton vacuum under 0.1 mbar vacuum pressure and then coated for 60 s with a gold powder layer using an Agar high-resolution sputter coater (model 208RH), equipped with a gold target/Agar thickness monitor controller. Micrographs with different magnifications were taken using the video capture computer program InterVideo WinDVR from InterVideo Inc.

In vitro degradation test

To simulate the behavior of the scaffolds when surrounded by living tissue, the PLA fibers of known weight were tested in a SBF-buffer solution (Simulated Body Fluid) according to ISO 15814:1999E. The buffer consisted of potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH₂PO₄) and disodium hydrogen phosphate (Na₂HPO₄·2H₂O) dissolved in distilled water. Samples were periodically taken from the medium, washed with distilled water and dried over night at room temperature. The

degradation was monitored with tensile test and mass remained after drying.

Fabrication of scaffolds

The melt-spun PLA fibers were woven into a 3D orthogonal woven structure using a handloom. The 3D orthogonal woven structure had three fiber filaments in three principal directions; five layers of warp, six layers of weft and 1/1 Z was used for the binding yarns.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mechanical properties

Hot-drawing was carried out at various temperatures between 65-75°C in order to investigate the effects of the drawing temperature. The drawing temperatures were slightly above the glass transition temperature (T_g) that was around 61°C for the as-spun PLA fibers. Hot-drawing at/or above 80°C was not possible because the fibers appeared to melt.

The tensile strength, tensile modulus and elongation at break of the as-spun fibers and fibers drawn between 65-75°C to various DRs are shown in Fig 1. It was apparent that the PLA-70 fibers (70 corresponds to the drawing temperature) at DR 5 showed the highest value at tensile strength, i.e. 20 cN/Tex. However, one unanticipated finding was the increases in elongation at break for the PLA fibers drawn at 65°C. Usually the elongation at break is expected to decrease with increased DR, since high DR is a way to increase the orientation in the fiber [11]. This discrepancy results may be due to that the chain folds in the polymer at this drawing temperature became unstable and disordered the crystallites. The polymer was instead quenched to an amorphous state [12], which resulted in a high elongation and a low tensile strength.

Thermal properties

All of the DSC scans exhibited a glass transition temperature (T_g) in the range of 63.4 – 73.7°C for the drawn PLA fibers. Comparing to the as-pun fiber, these values are slightly higher than that of undrawn fiber. The melting temperature (T_m) was detected around 168°C irrespective of DRs and drawing temperatures.

Figure 1. (top) tensile strength and (bottom) elongation at break of PLA fibers drawn at various temperatures of 65-75°C and draw-ratios of 3-6.

An exothermic peak between 79-124°C, representing cold crystallization, was observed and tended to be smaller and shifted to a lower temperature with increasing degree of crystallinity. The DSC results obtained from the first heating scans are presented in Table 1.

The most obvious differences appear to be at drawing temperature 65°C. The degree of crystallinity at this temperature was observed to stay rather low and decreased with increasing DRs. It might be assumed that the drawing temperature was too close the glass transition temperature (60.9°C for as-spun fibers) to allow an orientation of the macromolecules and instead the fibers became

overdrawn leading to a rather weak fiber. At higher drawing temperatures (70°C and 75°C) the degree of crystallinity is significantly improved. However, the drawing temperature seemed to be not the only parameter which affected the degree of crystallinity. It was also seen that the degree of crystallinity of the hot-drawn fiber increased as the DR is increased up to 5. The degree of crystallinity tended to decrease after this DR. It can be confirmed from the DSC that the degree of crystallinity reached a maximum at drawing temperature 70°C, thus resulting in the higher mechanical strength.

Table 1. DSC measurements of the as-spun and the drawn PLA fibers.

Sample	DR	T_g (°C)	T_c (°C)	Crystallinity (%)
PLA as-spun	-	60.9 ± 0.5	124.0 ± 2.1	13.4 ± 0.5
PLA-65	3	68.5 ± 0.2	81.9 ± 0.1	35.5 ± 0.2
	4	68.4 ± 0.2	121.4 ± 0.3	35.1 ± 0.6
	5	63.5 ± 0.9	117.1 ± 0.9	17.0 ± 0.2
	6	63.8 ± 0.4	119.6 ± 0.5	14.0 ± 0.9
PLA-70	3	71.8 ± 0.8	80.7 ± 0.2	41.1 ± 1.7
	4	72.5 ± 0.1	81.0 ± 0.1	42.9 ± 1.3
	5	72.1 ± 0.3	82.1 ± 0.7	45.8 ± 0.4
	6	71.3 ± 0.1	82.1 ± 0.8	45.4 ± 0.8
PLA-75	3	67.9 ± 0.0	79.0 ± 0.0	39.7 ± 1.3
	4	73.4 ± 0.5	82.6 ± 0.1	41.3 ± 0.8
	5	72.9 ± 0.5	83.1 ± 0.3	43.2 ± 3.6
	6	73.5 ± 0.2	83.0 ± 0.3	39.5 ± 0.0

Fig 2 shows the storage modulus (E'), the loss modulus (E'') and the $\tan \delta$ curves of the PLA-70 fibers with DR 3-6. The highest E' value, which reflected the material stiffness, was obtained at DR 5 that has an average value of 4.8 GPa at 37°C. The $\tan \delta$ vs. temperature curves for the PLA-70 fibers showed the peaks in the vicinity of 86°C, which were considered to correspond to the T_g . However, it is important to note that, when T_g is determined with DMTA, the material is under mechanical stress, as opposed to DSC. Therefore, the obtained data cannot be directly compared together. Anyway, the results confirmed that the drawing process at different speeds was important in order to increase the orientation in the fibers and one can conclude that, in the present case, the draw ratio of 5 is most suitable with regard to the strength.

Figure 2. DMTA thermograms for the drawn PLA fibers at 70°C with different DRs.

Morphological and micro-structural aspects

The surface morphology of the fibers is an important issue in order to establish the effect of the drawing of the fibers. From the optical microscope images in Fig 3, the as-spun PLA fibers resulted in a transparent fiber and the average diameter of the as-spun fibers was around 340 μm. After drawing, the fiber gradually lost transparency and became opaque with increasing the draw ratio. Recent developments in the field of producing melt spun PLA fibers have suggested that an increase in opacity of the fibers is a result of surface crazes. Surface crazes are generated in the fiber in the drawing process, due to overdrawing. The obtained fibers then resulted in low density and whitening, subsequently low tensile strength [13, 14]. However, the findings of the current study do not support this and SEM revealed that the surface of the drawn fibers was smooth and cracks were not presented (Fig 4).

Figure 3. Stereo-optical micrographs of; (Top) the Melt-spun PLA fiber (undrawn) and (Bottom) the drawn PLA fiber (drawn X6). The scale bars correspond to 100 μm .

Figure 4. FE-SEM image of the PLA-70 fiber with DR 5.

Degradability of melt-spun PLA fibers

Fig 5 shows the changes in tensile strength of the PLA-70 fibers with DR 5 and the mass loss as a function of the degradation time in the SBF solution. During the first week of degradation the tensile strength decreased with ca. 12% and after that it decreased with less than 1% per week. After 6 weeks, it showed a sudden drop in the strength. The percentage of mass loss can be used to estimate the degree of erosion associated with the degradation process [15]. However, up to the 10 weeks *in vitro* test the mass loss was not detected. This finding, while preliminary, suggests that bulk degradation took place in the fibers since the tensile strength decreases and no mass loss occurred.

Figure 5. (◆) Tensile strength and (■) mass loss of the PLA-70 fibers with DR 5 as a function of the degradation time in SBF buffer solution at 37°C.

Scaffold constructions

The aim of this study was to assess the mechanical properties of the melt-spun PLA fibers in such a way that they could be used as woven scaffolds for bone tissue engineering. Besides the fact that the PLA fibers require good mechanical properties in order to perform as scaffolds for bone tissue engineering, it is also necessary when the 3D porous scaffolds are formed because they are under high-tension conditions. For that reason, the 3D orthogonal woven scaffold was produced using the PLA-70 fibers with DR 5, since the highest value for tensile modulus and tensile strength achieved for these fibers. The schematic architecture in a target woven structure and the woven scaffold of the melt-spun PLA fibers are shown in Fig 6.

Figure 6. (Left) Woven prototype using polyester yarn. Width ~ 7 cm; (Right) 3D woven scaffold of melt-spun PLA fibers. Width ~ 1.5 cm.

The result drawn here is that the melt-spun PLA fibers have the great potential to be processed into 3D woven scaffolds with various porosity, pore size and shape. However, further research needs to be

done to investigate the woven scaffold in human clinical applications.

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